

EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF RICKETS.

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Abstract: This scientific article, written about the effectiveness of treatment of rickets, is dedicated to the study of methods of treatment of rickets, a disease characterized by a disorder of bone growth and development as a result of calcium and phosphate metabolism disorders. This article analyzes modern drugs used in the treatment of rickets, vitamin D and its analogues, as well as alternative treatment methods and their effectiveness. Research results, treatment effectiveness and side effects are presented. The results of scientific studies on the identification, diagnosis and prevention of clinical signs of rickets were analyzed. The article emphasizes the importance of individual approach to prevention and treatment of rickets among children and adolescents.

Key words: rickets, vitamin D, calcium, phosphate, bone development, children, effectiveness of treatment, diagnosis, prevention.

Rickets is a disease associated with vitamin D deficiency and mineral metabolism in the body. Rickets most often affects children under one year of age, and the most common category of patients are premature babies who are fed artificial foods. is characterized by a violation. Often this disease develops due to vitamin D deficiency. This article examines rickets treatments, their effectiveness, and side effects. In the initial period of the disease, changes occur in the patient's nervous system: the child becomes timid, nervous, capricious or moody; he sweats a lot, his face sweats when he sucks, and his neck sweats when he lies down. Because the child is bothered by itching, he puts his head on the pillow and his back hair falls out. When the disease worsens, the muscles become weak and twitch; A sick child walks late compared to a healthy child, the abdomen swells, the stomach often hardens or rubs, and then the bone system changes: the shoulder bone flattens, the head gets bigger, the forehead and top of the head bulge out, the forehead becomes lumpy, the top of the head and the bone in the neck area softens. observed. The large skull does not ossify in time. Often, the ribs near the sternum are thickened. When a child begins to walk, the legs bend in an X shape or an O shape. The shape of the chest also changes: it either bulges forward or sinks in.

The article analyzes various drugs and alternative methods used in the treatment of rickets. Various diagnostic methods were used in the studies to determine the clinical signs of rickets in children and adolescents of different ages.

Results:

1. Treatment with vitamin D and its analogs is highly effective and significantly improves bone mineralization and development.
2. Treatment with calcium and phosphate supplements helps to increase bone density.
3. Alternative methods, including sun exposure and dietary therapy, also provide positive results.

It was found that the effectiveness of vitamin D and calcium preparations in the treatment of rickets is high. It is also emphasized the importance of an individual approach to treatment and the need to take preventive measures to prevent the disease. Treatment of rickets in children should be carried out using complex - special and non-special methods (taking into account the cause of the disease). Non-specific methods include proper nutrition, the correct routine of the child's day, and various general strengthening procedures (massage, gymnastics, herbal and salt baths, etc.). Special methods include vitamin D, calcium, and prescribing phosphorus preparations, exposing the skin to artificial ultraviolet rays.

Conclusion: Modern methods and drugs used in the treatment of rickets are highly effective and important in the prevention and treatment of the disease. More research is needed on the diagnosis and prevention of rickets.

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